

OUR EVALUATIONS COUNT! CONVEYING OBLIGATION IN ENGLISH

PRIMERA LENGUA EXTRANJERA: INGLÉS 6º EP

PRESENTACIÓN

Cada vez es mayor la frecuencia con la que las personas emprendemos viajes cortos o largos a diferentes lugares del mundo. Nuestros padres o familiares hablan con personas que ya han estado en estos lugares o leen reseñas en internet para informarse sobre dichos lugares, y saber si deben visitarlos o no. Estas reseñas muestran las evaluaciones de otros adultos que ya han estado en ese lugar, pero ¿qué pasa con las evaluaciones de los niños y niñas que ya han estado allí? En esta secuencia didáctica vamos a aprender a evaluar lugares del mundo en donde hayamos estado, ofreciendo directrices, recomendaciones fuertes, y consejos a amigos o amigas, y a otros niños o niñas para que los visiten o no. Para ello, como objetivo final, escribiremos una breve reseña sobre un lugar en el que hayamos estado, animando a nuestros lectores a ir o no a través de los distintos usos de la obligación que se observan en las formas de *have to*, *must*, y *should* en inglés, a partir de una pequeña guía ofrecida por el profesor o la profesora. La reseña sobre un lugar turístico es un género discursivo muy común, especialmente en internet, que suele presentar las siguientes características:

- Es un breve texto que incluye información escrita sobre un lugar e imágenes
- Puede contener un eslogan
- Contiene información sobre el escritor (nombre real o ficticio, imagen generalmente ficticia con la que se identifica)
- Contiene usos de la obligación en forma de directrices, recomendaciones fuertes, y consejos para el lector
- Muchas veces contiene una evaluación numérica del lugar

Let's start!

DESARROLLO DE LA SECUENCIA DIDÁCTICA

PHASE 1

Session 1, 2 & 3

We have a problem: Las reseñas de internet sobre sitios, hoteles y restaurantes están normalmente escritas por adultos, ¿qué pasa con nosotros (niños y niñas)? ¡Muchas veces no pensamos igual que los adultos!

OUR EVALUATIONS COUNT!

What we will do: Observaremos y analizaremos distintas reseñas sobre lugares del mundo, prestando atención a cómo el hablante los evalúa, y ofrece directrices, recomendaciones fuertes, y consejos al lector o espectador. Esto nos ayudará a escribir una reseña sobre un lugar para otros niños y niñas que lo vayan a visitar.

What we will learn: Que una reseña puede estar escrita en tiempo pasado y presente; contiene palabras que describen el lugar y expresan la evaluación del hablante; contiene verbos modales que expresan obligación y sirven para dar directrices, recomendaciones fuertes o consejos al lector.

Activity 1 (in pairs)

A. Watch the following YouTube video of Abi and Lauren evaluating the National History Museum in London. You can watch it more than once, following the subtitles.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uLvFrkFkKIo>

A: Hi I'm Abi

L: I'm Lauren. We went to the Natural History Museum yesterday

A: My best bit was the earthquake

L: We went up the escalators into the World. It was amazing!

A: We went into the red zone. It was about the human evolution

L: I give it an 8 out of 10

A: I give it a 9 out of 10

L: Here's a tip, you **should** go at the last hour of the day when it's not so busy and the crowds are less busy.

A: Hola, yo soy Abi.

L: Yo Lauren. Ayer fuimos al Museo Nacional de Historia.

A: La mejor parte fue el terremoto.

L: Subimos por las escaleas mecánicas hacia el interior del Mundo. ¡Fue increíble!

A: Fuimos a la zona roja. Era sobre la evolución humana.

L: Yo le doy un 8 de 10.

A: Yo le doy un 9 de 10.

L: Un consejo, **deberías/deberíais** ir a última hora del día cuando no hay tanta gente y la multitud es menos... grande.

A: Hola, jo soc Abi.

L: Jo Lauren. Ahir anàrem al Museu Nacional de Història.

A: La millor part va ser el terratrèmol.

L: Pujàrem per les escales mecàniques cap a dintre del Mon. ¡Va ser increïble!

A: Anàrem a la zona roja. Era sobre l'evolució humana.

L: Jo li done un 8 de 10.

A: Jo li done un 9 de 10.

L: Un consell, **hauries/hauríeu d'**anar-hi a última hora del dia quan no n'hi ha tanta gent i la multitud es menys... gran.

B. Read the subtitles again, and answer the following questions.

- ✓ How are Abi's and Lauren's evaluations of the National History Museum? Positive? Negative? Circle words that indicate their evaluations.
- ✓ Look at Lauren's last sentence in English, Spanish, and Valencian. Write these sentences in the table below.

LAUREN	
SPANISH	
VALENCIAN	

Activity 2 (in pairs)

- ✓ Look at the verb **should** in Lauren's last sentence. It expresses obligation. Which kind of obligation? Select one of the following options.

STRONG

MEDIUM

WEAK

- ✓ Explain your answer briefly in your language.

- ✓ Subraya el verbo después de **should**. ¿Podemos usar **should** sin este verbo? (¿Podemos decir **you should at the last hour of the day*”, *“*deberías/deberíais a última hora del día”*?). Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

Activity 3 (in pairs)

MUSÉE DU LOUVRE

Photo source: pixabay

A. Read the following reviews of the Louvre written by an adult and a child.

Adult review of the Louvre
AN ABSOLUTE MUST-DO!

Dec 21

Last summer we visited the Louvre in Paris. The Louvre is an art museum. You **must** bring your own water, because there are no drinking fountains inside. We really enjoyed our visit. It was wonderful!

Child review of the Louvre
A BORING PLACE WITH NOTHING TO DO!

Last summer we went to the Louvre in Paris. It's a place full of paintings that I didn't understand. There are long queues to get in, so you **have to** be there early. It's a boring place full of people!

Dec 21

Vocabulary list:

drinking fountains: fuentes para beber *queues:* colas

B. Respond to the following questions. You can use your own language, if necessary.

- ✓ What's the slogan in each review? What does the adult's slogan mean? Use your own language to explain its meaning.

- ✓ How is the adult's evaluation of the Louvre? Positive? Negative? Circle words that indicate this evaluation.
- ✓ How is the child's evaluation of the Louvre? Positive? Negative? Circle words that indicate this evaluation.
- ✓ Look at the adult's and the child's sentences below. How would you say the same in Spanish and Valencian? Write your answers in the table.

	YOU (SPANISH)	YOU (VALENCIAN)
ADULT: ...You must bring your own water		

CHILD: ...you have to be there early		
--	--	--

Activity 4 (in pairs)

- ✓ Look at the verb **must** in the adult's review. It expresses obligation in English. Which kind of obligation? Select one of the following options.

- STRONG**
- MEDIUM**
- WEAK**

- ✓ Explain your answer briefly in your own language.

- ✓ Look at the verb **have to** in the child's review. It expresses obligation in English. Which kind of obligation? Select one of the following options.

- STRONG**
- MEDIUM**
- WEAK**

- ✓ Explain your answer briefly in your language.

- ✓ Subraya los verbos después de **must** y **have to**. ¿Podemos usar **must** y **have to** después de estos verbos? (¿Podemos decir **you must water with you*, "**debes agua contigo*"?). Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

¿Qué hemos aprendido?...

- Complete the text by selecting one option within the parentheses. Then use (√) where the characteristic applies.

Should, must, y have to _____ (*necesitan / no necesitan*) ir seguidos de otros verbos para tener sentido. Se llaman **verbos modales** porque expresan _____ (*la acción / el modo*) o manera en que se hace la acción del verbo que les sigue: _____ (*no obligada / obligada*).

OBLIGATION	Should	Must	Have to
Weak			
Medium			
Strong			

PHASE 2

Sessions 3, 4 & 5

Activity 5 (in pairs)

A. Read the following children's reviews of two touristic attractions in Australia.

1. MOVIE WORLD

Date: 06 Sep 2015

User: eddieffat

Movie World is the best place for kids' entertainment. Movie World has very friendly staff that are happy to help you. You **should** try its nice restaurants. Movie World is fun!

2. EAGLEHAWK DIVE CENTRE

Date: 06 Feb 2016

User: xyith

Eaglehawk dive centre is one of my favourite places. You **have to** be there early, if you want to avoid a long queue. You **mustn't** feed the fish, because it's forbidden. There is a delicious cafe at the entrance, and a gift shop that you **shouldn't** miss. It's awesome! You **must** try diving at Eaglehawk!

Vocabulary list

friendly: amistoso o amistosa
staff: personal, empleados y empleadas
avoid: evitar
feed: alimentar, dar de comer

forbidden: prohibido
miss: perderse algo
cafe: cafeteria
gift shop: tienda de souvenirs o regalos

- Write a slogan for each of the reviews at their top. Be brief and use your imagination!
- Write similar words in Spanish and Valencian to reviewers' positive words below. You can use a dictionary, if you need it.

SPANISH	ENGLISH	VALENCIAN
	the best place	
	friendly	
	happy	
	nice	
	it's fun	
	one of my favourite places	
	delicious	
	it's awesome	

- Circle the positive words in the table that are most similar in English, Spanish and Valencian. Similar words in different languages are called **Cognates**.
- Classify the modal verbs in purple according to their obligation meaning (weak, medium, strong).

OBLIGATION MEANING		
WEAK	MEDIUM	STRONG

- Reviewers use modal verbs in purple to give readers advice, strong recommendations, and directives. Classify them according to their uses.

USES		
ADVICE	STRONG RECOMMENDATIONS	DIRECTIVES

B. Look at the modal verbs in the table below. How would you say the same in Spanish and Valencian? Write your answers in the table.

MOVIE WORLD	
ENGLISH	You should try its nice restaurants
YOU (SPANISH)	
YOU (VALENCIAN)	

EAGLEHAWK DIVE CENTRE	
ENGLISH	You have to be there early You mustn't feed the fish ... a gift shop that you shouldn't miss You must try diving
YOU (SPANISH)	
YOU (VALENCIAN)	

Activity 6 (in pairs)

- Read the following children's reviews. Complete the texts selecting one option within the parentheses.

REVIEW 1

Travellinggirl30

Portsmouth, United Kingdom • 4 contributions

Dec 2018

Photo source: The Telegraph

My parents and I stayed at this nice hotel in Miami. The chicken nuggets at the hotel's restaurant were horrible. You _____ (*mustn't / shouldn't*) eat them. What an awful place!

Vocabulary

awful: terrible, horroroso

- ✓ En el texto anterior, ¿es posible usar *mustn't* y *shouldn't* o solo uno? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

REVIEW 2

Review of Stonehenge

Oct 2015

Honestlocal2012

I was disgusted to find that this place was just a few rocks. You _____ (*mustn't / shouldn't*) litter there. It's forbidden. I _____ (*should / must*) apologize to readers, but to me it's a silly place!.

Photo Source: pixabay

Vocabulary:

litter: tirar papeles, latas (basura)

apologize: disculparse

- ✓ En la oración "You (*mustn't / shouldn't*) litter there" ¿es posible usar *mustn't* y

shouldn't o solo uno? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

✓ En la oración "I (*should / must*) apologize to readers" ¿es posible usar *should* y *must* o solo uno? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

REVIEW 3

Nov 2022

Photo source: pixabay

You (*have to / should*) _____ visit Versailles when you're in Paris. You _____ (*should / have to*) book an audio guide, if you want to understand the context of everything you will see. I learnt a lot!

Vocabulary:

book: reservar

✓ En la oración "You (*have to / should*) visit Versailles" ¿es posible usar *have to* y *should* o solo uno? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

- ✓ En la oración “You (*have to / should*) book an audio guide” ¿es posible usar *should* y *must*? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

- Write a slogan for each of the reviews at their top. Be brief and use your imagination!
- Write similar words in Spanish and Valencian to reviewers’ negative words below. You can use a dictionary, if you need it.

SPANISH	ENGLISH	VALENCIAN
	horrible	
	awful	
	disgusted	
	silly	

- Circle the negative words in the table that are most similar in English, Spanish and Valencian. Similar words in different languages are called **Cognates**.

¿Qué hemos aprendido?...

- Complete the table below by using (✓) where the characteristic applies.

USES	Should	Must	Have to
Is used to give ADVICE			
Is used to offer a STRONG RECOMMENDATION			
Is used to give DIRECTIVES			

OTHER CHARACTERISTICS	Should	Must	Have to
Is used for rules and prohibitions			
Is used for moral obligation			
Is used in informal contexts and conversation			

PHASE 3

Sessions 7 & 8

Activity 7 (in pairs)

- Read the negative review of The Big Ben in London. Write a positive review in the space at the right using opposite obligation verbs and words. To organise your writing, you can use the table below.

THE BIG BEN

Photo source: pixabay

Not so BIG BEN!

Review of Big Ben

Nov 2016

[Honestlocal2012](#)

I went last week to the famous 'Big Ben'.
 We **should** rename it 'Medium Ben',
 because they **should** build it higher. The
 tower is **horrible** and the bell is **old**. The
 stairs are **dangerous**. It's an attraction that
 you **mustn't** see, because it's **useless**. In
 sum, it's something that you **have to** miss!

AFFIRMATIVE VERB FORMS	NEGATIVE VERB FORMS
should	
	mustn't
have to	
POSITIVE WORDS	NEGATIVE WORDS
	horrible
	old
	dangerous
	useless

Activity 8

- Select **should, shouldn't, must, mustn't** or **have to** where necessary.

An ancient jewel

Last summer, we travelled to Rome and visited The Colosseum. You _____ visit this amazing building, in which gladiators used to fight against wild animals. All visitors _____ book a ticket in advance online, but if you have a Roma Pass, you _____ worry. If you want to see the arena, you _____ buy a special

ticket. If you have a pet, you _____ bring it, because they are not allowed. I highly recommend you to book a tour in advance too. There is a lot of security at the entrance, so you _____ bring any dangerous object in your bag. You also _____ go there early, because it gets very busy. In short, visiting the Colosseum is an experience you _____ miss.

Vocabulary:

gladiators: gladiadores

wild animals: animales salvajes

allowed: permitido

security: seguridad

Amy4am

April, 2022

Photo source: pixabay

- ✓ How can we say the underlined sentence above using a modal verb in English?

- ✓ ¿Qué verbo modal has usado en la oración “If you have a pet, you...”. ¿Por qué? Razona brevemente tu respuesta.

Now you write! (in pairs)

- Think of a place that you have visited. Write a review following these steps:

A. We plan:

1. **Which place** (attraction, museum, building, hotel, etc.) will you review?
2. **Select pictures of this place.** Scan them or download them from the Internet and save them in your computer.
3. **Select a picture for your reviewer identity:** an avatar, animal, your face... Scan or download them from the Internet and save them in your computer.

4. **Set readers in context:**

- When did you visit the place?
- What's its location (city, region, country, ...)?
- How did you get there (by plain, bus, car...)?

5. **Mention some characteristics.** Use the tables below.

- Useful expressions: *This place is famous / popular, because...; This place is famous because of its history...*

Is it a famous or popular place? Why?

- Useful expressions: *There is a... / There are...; You can find...*

What can you find there? Any facilities? toilettes, shops, restaurants, cafes, parking spaces, buses...Any spaces? A lake, a forest, a field, a beach,...

What can you find there? Things such as water, sand, trees, plants, flowers, rocks, paintings, sculptures, drinking fountains, a rollercoaster,...or animals such as farm animals, wild animals, fish...

How can you access the place? Is free? Do you need to buy a ticket, pass...? Where do you buy it? Is there security at the entrance?

6. **Mention what you did there.** Write brief notes in the space below.

B. We write:

7. Write all the information in 2) as an Introduction to your review:

8. Is your evaluation positive? Negative? Use the information in 3) and 4) to write positive or negative words about the place and what you did there. Look at the examples.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PLACE	
POSITIVE WORDS	NEGATIVE WORDS
<i>There are nice toilettes. The toilettes are big.</i>	<i>The toilettes are disgusting</i>

WHAT YOU DID	
POSITIVE WORDS	NEGATIVE WORDS
<i>It was amazing.</i>	<i>There is always a long queue at the entrance.</i>

9. Use **should, shouldn't, must, mustn't and have to** in order to advice, strongly recommend or direct readers to visit or not to visit the place.

10. Write a brief conclusion: How was your experience in general? Will you come back?

C. Put all the information together in this template and revise your writing.

YOUR NICKNAME HERE
DATE OF REVIEW HERE

A PICTURE HERE

YOUR PICTURE
HERE

YOUR SLOGAN HERE

Your review here

A PICTURE HERE

¿Qué hemos aprendido?...

- Complete the text by selecting one option within the parentheses.

Las reseñas tienen en su parte superior un _____ (*título / eslogan*), que es una frase corta que indica la motivación, acción o intención del hablante sobre el tema, y pretende captar su atención. En ellas expresamos nuestra evaluación positiva o negativa, y damos a los lectores consejos a través de _____ (**should / must / have to**), recomendaciones fuertes a través de _____ (**should / must / have to**), y directrices a través de _____ (**should / must / have to**). Estos verbos expresan, por tanto, obligación. **Should** expresa obligación _____ (*débil / intermedia / fuerte*); **must** expresa obligación _____ (*débil / intermedia / fuerte*), y **have to** expresa obligación _____ (*débil / intermedia / fuerte*). _____ (**should / must / have to**) se usa además para obligación moral, reglas y prohibiciones. _____ (**should / must / have to**) se usa en contextos informales y en la conversación. Estos verbos se llaman _____ (*verbos léxicos / verbos modales*) porque se refieren al modo en que se hace la acción del verbo que les sigue: de un modo _____ (*no obligado / obligado*). Por tanto, _____ (*necesitan / no necesitan*) ir seguidos de otros verbos para tener sentido.